

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Checklist of butterflies from the Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) premises, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

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Abstract: Butterfly diversity and abundance at the Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) were studied from July 2021 to December 2021. A total of 322 individuals belonging to 21 species from 5 families were recorded. Based on family-wise species comparison, Nymphalidae was the most diversified with eight species, representing 38% of the total species of butterflies, followed by Pieridae with five species, representing 24% of the total species. The lowest number of species was recorded in Hesperiidae, with two species representing 10% of the total. Diversity and abundance of butterflies showed variation among seasons, and results showed that the highest diversity was in the wet season, representing 56%, and the lowest was in the dry season, representing 44% of the identified species. The difference in diversity was not significant among seasons with $t = 1.883$, $df = 20$, and a p value of 0.074. Species accumulation curves for the dry and wet seasons showed that the number of new species declined during the dry season at 100 individuals sampled and at 150 individuals during the wet season. In general, habitat conservation and habitat enrichment with butterfly larval host and butterfly nectar plants would help to improve the butterfly diversity at Ethiopian biodiversity institute.

Key words: Biodiversity, Butterfly Abundance, Butterfly diversity

Introduction

The Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) is a government organization primarily established for the conservation and sustainable use of Ethiopia's biodiversity. The institute's head office is located in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, with an estimation of more than 30% of the total area covered by greenery, mainly grasses, ornamental flowers, and trees. As insects are associated with plant diversity (Lawton, 1983), a number of insect species can be found at the compound of the EBI. Butterflies are an important group of fauna because of their role in pollination (Thakur and Mattu, 2010), their attractiveness, their role as bio indicators as they are highly sensitive to any environmental changes (Lomov et al., 2006), and their role in food chains and food webs as sources of food for other organisms such as birds (Watt and Boggs, 2019). Thus, the current study focused on evaluating the diversity of butterflies at the EBI premises.

Butterflies, together with moths, grouped in the order Lepidoptera (Pullin, 2012). With over 180,000 species worldwide (Britannica 2021; Lepidoptera in GBIF Secretariat, 2021; Myers et al., 2022), the order Lepidoptera is the second biggest insect order (Britannica 2021; Lepidoptera in GBIF Secretariat, 2021; Myers et al (Pullin, 2012). Butterflies are an important part of the biodiversity of the world (Pullin, 2012). Butterflies (superfamily Papilionoidea) are divided into six families: brush-footed butterflies (family Nymphalidae), hairstreaks and blues (family Lycaenidae), whites and sulphurs (family Pieridae), swallowtail butterflies (family Papilionoidea), skippers (family Hesperiidae), and metalmarks (family Riodinidae). With the exception of the family Riodinidae, all are found in Ethiopia (Tujuba et al., 2019).

Beyond their attractiveness, butterflies are ecologically important creatures (Pullin, 2012). They have a strong correlation with the diversity of plants. The greater the diversity of butterflies in a habitat, the greater the diversity of plants which serve as a source of food for both larvae and adult butterflies (Lomov et al., 2006). Additionally, butterflies are an indicator of a healthy ecosystem (Adrade, 1998; Thakur and Mattu, 2010). Regrettably, butterflies are declining by habitat degradation and fragmentation (Lawton, 1983). Human activity has a significant impact on the richness, abundance, and diversity of butterfly species as a result of destroying naturally grown nectar and larval host plants that house eggs, larvae, and pupae (Van Dyck et al., 2009). Thus, studying the diversity of butterflies at different habitats helps the in-situ conservation. Therefore, this research was focused to provide primary information on butterfly diversity at the EBI premises.

Materials and methods

Study Area

Ethiopian biodiversity institute (EBI) is situated in the Yeka sub city of Addis Ababa city administration at latitude of 9.0337454 and longitude 38.7818385 and elevation of 2,429 meter above sea level (Figure 1). EBI is bordered with Kenya embassy by east, Russia embassy by west, Comoros street by south and Yeka lidet church by north. The current study was conducted at EBI premises from July 2021 to December 2021 for six months. *Cordia africana*, *Terminalia laxiflora*, *Sida rhombifolia*, *Grewia mollis*, *Aloe vera*, *Carissa spinarum*, *Millettia ferruginea*, *Urtica simensis*, and *Vernonia amygdalina* are among the tree species present on the property. The average annual maximum temperature is about 28°C. The average minimum temperature is about 8°C, and the average annual rainfall is about 102mm.

Figure 1: Map of Ethiopian biodiversity institute (EBI) (by Tadesse Hunduma)

Butterfly Survey

The butterflies were surveyed utilizing purposive sampling throughout the entire compound twice a month from July to December 2021, for a total of 12 times during the survey. Butterfly collecting and observation took place from 8:00 am to 11:00 am in the morning and 2:00 pm to 4:00 pm in the afternoon, as butterflies are sensitive to environmental conditions (Woodhall, 2020).

Butterfly identification

Identification butterflies was conducted based on external morphological features and comparison of the photographs with the help of field guides (Ratnasingham and Hebert, 2007; Nugent, 2018; Woodhall, 2020; Lepidoptera in GBIF Secretariat, 2021). All voucher specimens were kept at the Ethiopian biodiversity institute laboratory.

Data analysis

The collected data were used to calculate species richness (S), species abundance, species diversity (Shannon Weiner index and Simpson’s diversity index), and Pielou’s evenness index for dry and wet seasons. Raw data of species richness counts of six months from each sampling site were pooled to get rarefaction curves for comparison of estimated species richness between the seasons. PAST version 4.10 version was used to calculate diversity indices, cluster analysis,

species rarefaction curves, and species richness estimates. T-test was used to compare species composition between different seasons.

Results

Butterfly fauna at Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) compound

Our assessment revealed that a total of 322 individuals belonging to 21 species from 5 families were recorded (Table 1). Based on family wise species comparison, Nymphalidae had the highest richness with eight species, representing 38% (103 individuals) of the total collected, followed by Pieridae with five species, representing 24% of the total species. The lowest number of species was recorded in Hesperiiidae with 2 species representing 10% of the total number of butterfly species (Figure 2; Table 1).

Table 1: Family wise composition of butterflies at Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI)

Family name	Number of species	Number of individuals
Nymphalidae	8	103
Pieridae	5	143
Papilionidae	3	33
Lycanidae	3	29
Hesperiiidae	2	14

Figure 2: Composition of butterfly species of each family recorded at Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) showing uneven distribution species richness across the families

When family wise abundance was considered, Pieridae had the highest abundance (143 individuals), representing 45% of the total collected, followed by Nymphalidae (103 individuals), representing 32% of the total whereas the lower abundances were recorded in family Lycanidae with 29 individuals representing 9% and Hesperiiidae with 14 individuals representing 4% of the total collected butterflies (Table 1 and Figure 3).

Figure 3: Composition of butterflies based on species abundance for each family recorded at EBI

Seasonal butterfly diversity at Ethiopian biodiversity institute (EBI)

Diversity and abundance of butterflies showed variation among seasons, and results showed that the highest diversity recorded in the wet season with 18 species representing 56% and the lowest recorded in the dry season with 14 species representing 44% of the identified species from the EBI compound (Table 1; Table 2).

The abundance of butterflies also varies among seasons, such that the highest was recorded during the wet season, representing 65% (208 individuals), and the rest (35%, 114 individuals) was recorded during the dry season (Table 2 and 3). *Belenois aurota* (Pieridae) with 48 individuals and *Colias electo* (Pieridae) with 35 species were ranked the first and second most abundant butterfly species, whereas *Anthene definite* (Lycanidae) and *Charaxes candiope* (Nymphalidae) with 4 butterflies each was ranked the least (Table 3). *Charaxes candiope*, *Junonia hierta*, *Junonia oenone*, *Junonia Sophia*, *Junonia terea*, *Belenois raffrayi*, and *Colias electo* were only recorded in the wet season, and *Anthene definite*, *Anthene opalina*, and *Zizula hylax* were recorded in the dry season only (Table 3).

Table 2: Seasonal composition of butterflies at EBI

Season	Number of species (%)	Number of Individuals (%)
Wet season	18 (56%)	208 (65%)
Dry season	14 (44%)	114 (35%)
Total	32	322

Table 3: Checklist of species composition of butterflies at Ethiopian biodiversity institute (EBI).

Family	Common name	Scientific name	Wet season	Dry season	Total
Nymphalidae	Green Veined Charaxes	<i>Charaxes candiope</i> (Godart, 1824)	4	0	4
	Danaid eggfly	<i>Hypolimnas misippus</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	8	4	12
		<i>Junnonia chroimene</i> (Guerin, 1844)	10	10	20
	Yellow pansy	<i>Junnonia hierta</i> (Trimen, 1870)	15	0	15
	Blue pansy	<i>Junonia oenone</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	10	0	10
	Little pansy	<i>Junonia Sophia</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	12	0	12
	Soldier pansy	<i>Junonia terea</i> (Drury, 1773)	8	0	8
	Painted lady	<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	10	12	22
Pieridae	Pioneer white	<i>Belenois aurota</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	25	23	48
	Raffray's white	<i>Belenois raffrayi</i> (Oberthür, 1878)	24	0	24
	African Migrant	<i>Catopsilia florella</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	12	6	18
	Clouded yellow	<i>Colias electo</i> (Linnaeus, 1763)	35	0	35
	Small grass yellow	<i>Eurema brigitta</i> (Stoll, 1780)	12	6	18
Papilionidae	African swallowtail	<i>Papilio dardanus</i> (Oberthür, 1883)	4	6	10
	Citrus Swallowtail	<i>Papilio demodocus</i> (Esper, 1798)	8	8	16
	Green-banded swallowtail	<i>Papilio nireus</i> (Felder & Felder, 1865)	4	3	7
Lycanidae	Ciliate blue	<i>Anthene definita</i> (Pagenstecher, 1902)	0	4	4
	Opal hairtail	<i>Anthene opalina</i> (Stempffer, 1946)	0	10	10
	Tiny grass blue	<i>Zizula hylax</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	0	15	15
Hesperiidae	Savanna elf	<i>Eretis lugens</i> (Rogenhofer, 1891)	3	2	5
		<i>Zenonia zeno</i> Trimen, 1864	4	5	9

The Simpson 1-D and Shannon H diversity indices for butterflies were calculated for both the dry and wet seasons, and the results revealed that the wet season had the highest Simpson 1-D and Shannon H with 0.92 and 2.7, respectively, and the dry season had the highest evenness index with Evenness $e^{H/S} = 0.87$ and Equitability = 0.95. (Table 4). With $t = 1.883$, $df = 20$, and a p value of 0.074, the difference in butterfly diversity and abundance across seasons was insignificant (Table 5). Figure 4 shows the species accumulation curves for the dry and wet seasons, showing that the number of new species declined during the dry season at 100 individuals sampled and at 150 individuals during the wet season.

Table 4: Diversity indices of butterflies

Season	Diversity indices				
	Simpson_1-D	Shannon_H	Evenness_e^H/S	Equitability_J	Fisher_alpha
Wet season	0.9201	2.707	0.8322	0.9364	4.729
Dry season	0.9048	2.501	0.871	0.9477	4.193

Table 5: Result of paired t-test among dry and wet season

	Paired Samples Test							
	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
			Lower	Upper				
Wet season – dry season	4.476	10.893	2.377	-.482	9.435	1.883	20	.074

Figure 4: Species accumulation curve of butterflies among dry and wet seasons

Discussion

This is the first study of the diversity and abundance butterflies in the EBI premises. The 21 species recorded in the compound represent about 5% of the total butterfly fauna of Ethiopia reported (Tujuba et al., 2019). Considering the smaller area of the premises, it can be considered that the number of butterfly species recorded was comparatively higher. However, the current result is lower than butterfly species recorded from Gullele Botanical Garden (46 butterfly species) (Jenber and Getu, 2020). The lower diversity of butterflies could be due to the size of the premises when comparing Gullele botanical garden. The second reason could be that the EBI premises is more disturbed than the Gullele botanical garden, and butterflies prefer undisturbed habitats (Adrade, 1998). Moreover, the butterfly numbers recorded during the current study were greater than the study reported by Wale and Abdella (2021), which reported 11 species. *Belenois aurota* and *Colias electo* were the most abundant species while *Anthene*

definite and *Charaxes candiope* were the least abundant species over all the the seasons. The overall butterfly species diversity and abundance revealed that the family Nymphalidae was the most diversified. This observation could be due to the wide distribution of Nymphalidae, ability to inhabit a wide range of ecological niches, and feeding on a diverse range of plants (they are generalists) (Hamm and Fordyce, 2015). Similar observations have been reported from different parts of Ethiopia (Norfolk et al., 2017; Jemal and Patharajan, 2018; Jenber and Getu, 2020; Wale and Abdella, 2021).

Family Hespariidae was the least represented based on the number of species, representing only 9% of the total collected species of butterflies. The limited number of host plants, less ability for habitat adaptation, and due to their dual color could be the reason for this observation (Koneri, R. and Maabuat, 2016). Diversity and abundance of butterflies showed variation among seasons, and results showed that the highest diversity and abundance was recorded in the wet season compared to the dry season. However, the difference in diversity and abundance was not statistically significant. The results of the current study contradict results from previous studies (Jenber and Getu, 2020; Schmitt et al., 2021; Jenber and Wili, 2021). Butterfly distribution and abundance are affected by changes in habitat and climate (Dennis, 1993; Pullin, 2012; Watt and Boggs, 2019). Butterfly diversity varies according to season, and abiotic conditions such as rainfall, temperature, and humidity which have a significant impact on the distribution and abundance of butterflies (Dennis, 1993; Jenber and Wili, 2021; Schmitt et al., 2021). However, the results of the current study contradict with the above. One of the reasons could be that the climatic variation had no effect on the movement of the butterflies and had no effect on the diversity of host plants.

Conclusion

A total of 322 individuals belonging to 21 species from 5 families were recorded from the current study. Family Nymphalidae was the most diversified family followed by Peiridae. The least diverse was family Hespariidae. The findings of the current study revealed that butterfly species diversity was not significantly different between dry and wet seasons. *Belenois aurota* and *Colias electo* were the most abundant species, and *Anthene definite* and *Charaxes candiope* were the least abundant species over all seasons. In general, habitat conservation and habitat enrichment with butterfly larval host and butterfly nectar plants would help to improve the butterfly diversity at EBI.

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